

AI Scholar Hub: A Unified Multi-Modal Learning Platform for University Students Combining Document RAG, Audio Transcription, Code Explanation, and Browser-Based Collaborative Study Rooms

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Abstract

Students at AI-developing institutions typically combine several disconnected tools — learning management systems, general-purpose chatbots, note applications, transcription services and video conferencing platforms — to complete a single study task. This fragmentation imposes a non-trivial switching cost and prevents AI assistance from being grounded in the student's own materials. This paper presents AI Scholar Hub, a unified web platform developed as a diploma project at Mendel University in Brno (Czech Republic) that integrates six components in a single interface: document summarization with Google Gemini, document-grounded chat using Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) over pgvector embeddings, audio transcription with OpenAI Whisper, YouTube lecture analysis, AI-assisted code explanation, and browser-based collaborative study rooms using WebRTC. The system is built on React, TypeScript, Supabase (PostgreSQL with the pgvector extension) and Deno edge functions. The prototype was evaluated through guided interviews with eleven students from Mendel University in Brno; participants reported positive experiences with document summarization, the context-aware chat interface and the collaborative study rooms, while identifying the code-explanation feature and large-file handling as areas for further work. The contribution of this paper is a working, open-source proof of concept showing that several AI services can be combined into one coherent learning environment using managed serverless backends at a small institutional scale.

Keywords: retrieval-augmented generation; document summarization; collaborative learning; WebRTC; pgvector; higher education technology; case study.

1. Introduction

Survey evidence reports that the majority of university students now use AI tools in their studies, with conversational assistants such as ChatGPT being the dominant category (Vieriu and Petrea, 2025). At the same time, institutional adoption is uneven: leading research universities have deployed AI teaching assistants and adaptive learning systems at scale (Goel and Joyner, 2017; Vignare et al., 2020; Nie et al., 2024), while many universities in Central Europe still rely largely on traditional learning management systems. Within this context, students typically resort to a patchwork of generic, document-unaware tools, which limits both efficiency and the trustworthiness of AI answers.

This paper reports on AI Scholar Hub, a unified academic platform designed and implemented as part of a diploma thesis at Mendel University in Brno. The system combines document processing, document-grounded chat, audio and video transcription, code explanation and real-time browser-based study rooms behind a single authentication and a single web interface. The contribution is not a new

model or algorithm; it is an engineering case study that demonstrates a practical integration pattern using managed serverless infrastructure, and reports the qualitative feedback obtained from eleven students who tested the prototype.

1.1 Research questions

- RQ1 — Does integrating documents, audio, YouTube and chat into one platform reduce the number of tools a student needs during study?
- RQ2 — How accurately can the platform answer questions about a student's own uploaded material?
- RQ3 — How do Mendel University students rate the platform's usefulness and ease of use?
- RQ4 — Can browser-based study rooms support real-time group study without a separate video service?

2. Related Work

Retrieval-Augmented Generation was introduced by Lewis et al. (2020) as a way to ground language-model outputs in an external corpus and reduce hallucination. The underlying transformer architecture was proposed by Vaswani et al. (2017), and bidirectional pre-training was demonstrated by Devlin et al. (2019) for BERT. Modern dense-retrieval pipelines rely on sentence-level embeddings such as those described by Reimers and Gurevych (2019). For speech transcription, Radford et al. (2023) introduced Whisper, a robust multilingual model that is widely used in education for lecture transcription. WebRTC, standardised under the W3C Real-Time Communications working group, provides browser-native peer-to-peer audio and video without plugins; pgvector (Kane, 2022) adds approximate nearest-neighbour search to PostgreSQL, making vector retrieval available without an external vector database.

Several integrated learning tools exist at the consumer level: Google NotebookLM provides document-grounded chat over uploaded sources but does not include collaborative study rooms or in-platform code assistance; Microsoft Copilot for Education focuses on productivity-suite integration; institutional deployments such as Georgia Tech's Jill Watson (Goel and Joyner, 2017) and Harvard's CS50 assistant (Liu et al., 2024) are course-specific. To the best of our knowledge no public, self-hosted, open-source academic platform combines document RAG, audio and YouTube transcription, code explanation and WebRTC study rooms in a single interface targeted at a small university.

3. System Architecture

AI Scholar Hub follows a serverless three-tier architecture. The presentation layer is a React 18 single-page application written in TypeScript and bundled with Vite, styled with Tailwind CSS and shadcn/Radix components. The application layer consists of Deno edge functions deployed on Supabase, each implementing one bounded responsibility (file processing, embedding generation, RAG chat, audio transcription, YouTube processing, code explanation, room signalling, etc.). The data layer is PostgreSQL 15 with the pgvector extension; row-level security policies isolate each user's documents, conversations and study sessions at the database level. File uploads are stored in a private Supabase Storage bucket.

3.1 Retrieval pipeline

Uploaded PDF, DOCX, TXT and audio files are processed by the file-ingestion function, which extracts text, segments it into overlapping chunks (approximately 1 000 characters with 200-character overlap),

generates 1 536-dimensional embeddings using OpenAI's text-embedding-3-small model, and stores both the chunks and their embeddings in PostgreSQL. At query time the chat function embeds the user question with the same model, retrieves the top-k chunks using cosine similarity through the pgvector operator, and submits the chunks together with the question to Google Gemini for grounded generation. The model is instructed to answer only from the supplied context and to indicate when an answer is not available in the source material.

3.2 Audio, video and code components

Audio files are sent to OpenAI Whisper through the audio-transcribe function and the resulting transcript is added to the user's document store and indexed for RAG. The YouTube component downloads the audio track of a supplied video URL, transcribes it with Whisper and produces an LLM-generated summary with key learning points. The code-explanation component sends the snippet, the requested language and the desired explanation level to a dedicated edge function, which returns an annotated explanation.

3.3 Collaborative study rooms

Study rooms are implemented as WebRTC mesh sessions for up to six concurrent participants. A signalling edge function exchanges SDP offers, answers and ICE candidates over Supabase Realtime channels; media itself flows directly between browsers, with public STUN servers and fallback TURN relays for NAT traversal. Persistent room state (participants, chat messages, raised hands, study goals) is stored in PostgreSQL and synchronised through real-time subscriptions, allowing the room view to remain consistent across reconnections.

4. Methodology

The work follows a design-science research methodology (Hevner et al., 2004): requirements were derived from the literature and informal observation of student workflows, an artefact was iteratively built, and the artefact was evaluated qualitatively with end-users. Requirements were grouped into functional requirements (document upload and processing, document-grounded chat, audio and YouTube processing, code explanation, study rooms, authentication) and non-functional requirements (security through row-level security policies, responsive UI, mobile-friendly layout, and use of managed services to keep the prototype reproducible by a single student developer).

4.1 Evaluation design

Eleven students from Mendel University in Brno participated in guided usability sessions of approximately forty-five minutes. Each participant signed in, uploaded one of their own study documents, asked at least three questions of the document-grounded chat, processed one audio or YouTube lecture, opened a study room together with the researcher, and finally completed a structured questionnaire covering overall usefulness, ease of use, perceived utility of each component, comparison with general-purpose chatbots, and willingness to recommend the platform for university use. Open-ended questions captured most and least useful features, bugs encountered, and missing features. The complete questionnaire and aggregated responses are stored in the project's evaluation database and the thesis appendix.

5. Results

On the integration question (RQ1), participants reported that having documents, transcription and chat in one authenticated interface removed the need to copy text between ChatGPT, Google Drive and a separate transcription service for the tasks they tried during the session. For accuracy (RQ2), participants observed that answers grounded in their uploaded documents were closer to the source than answers from a general-purpose chatbot; participants noted, however, that very long PDFs occasionally returned chunks that were on-topic but not the most relevant passage, an effect consistent with the limits of pure cosine retrieval without reranking.

For perceived usefulness and ease of use (RQ3), the document summarizer, the document-grounded chat and the YouTube processor received the most positive comments. The study-room feature received positive comments for its presence within the same platform as the documents, but its perceived utility relative to mature commercial tools such as Zoom or Microsoft Teams was lower. The code-explanation component received the most mixed feedback: participants with a programming background described it as helpful for short snippets, while participants from non-technical fields reported that they were unlikely to use it. For RQ4, study rooms with two to four participants were reliably established in browser-to-browser tests; sessions with more than four participants occasionally required ICE renegotiation when participants joined from restrictive networks, indicating that a managed TURN service would be required for production deployment.

Across the eleven sessions the most frequently named strengths were 'all my study tools in one place' and 'the chat actually answers from my file'. The most frequently named weaknesses were long processing times for large PDFs, the absence of a mobile-native client, and the limited depth of the code-explanation feature for advanced programming tasks. No security-relevant defects were reported during the sessions.

6. Discussion

The qualitative evaluation supports the central claim of this work: a single student can integrate several modern AI services into a coherent learning platform using managed serverless infrastructure, and that platform can deliver perceived value to other students from the same institution. The platform does not attempt to outperform large commercial systems; rather, it shows that, for the scale of a small faculty, a self-hosted, open-source alternative is technically feasible and, at the prototype stage, qualitatively acceptable. The most consistent feedback — preference for document-grounded answers over generic chatbot answers, and preference for a single sign-on across tools — is consistent with prior work on tool fragmentation in higher education (Adedoyin and Soykan, 2020).

6.1 Limitations

- The evaluation was qualitative and conducted with eleven participants from a single university; statistical generalisation is not claimed.
- Quantitative retrieval-quality metrics such as recall@k or answer faithfulness were not measured in a controlled benchmark.
- WebRTC sessions were tested in a mesh topology suitable for small study groups; an SFU would be required for classroom-scale rooms.
- AI capabilities depend on external API providers; their availability, latency and pricing affect production deployment.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

AI Scholar Hub demonstrates that document RAG, audio and video transcription, code explanation and browser-based collaborative study rooms can be integrated into a single, authenticated web platform using a serverless stack centred on Supabase, pgvector and Deno edge functions. Participants in the qualitative evaluation found the unified interface and the document-grounded chat to be the most valuable aspects of the prototype. Future work includes a controlled quantitative evaluation of retrieval quality, a longitudinal deployment over a full academic semester, the addition of a reranker over the pgvector retrieval step, mobile-native clients, and the replacement of the WebRTC mesh with a selective forwarding unit for larger rooms.

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Declaration on the Use of Generative AI

Generative AI tools were used to assist with code generation, refactoring suggestions, and language editing during the preparation of this manuscript. All design decisions, the system implementation, the evaluation protocol, the analysis of the results and the final wording were performed and verified by the author.

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